

Equitable and Quality Basic Science Education: Assessing Students' Learning in Junior Secondary Schools for Advancing Integrated Science in Tertiary Institutions

Oginni Aderonke Margaret¹

oginniam@lasued.edu.ng

08023150279

Awobodu Victoria Yetunde¹

awoboduvy@lasued.edu.ng

08035205940

Saibu Sakibu Olajide¹

saibuso@lasued.edu.ng

08129968859

Olude Adebisi Sylvester¹

oludeas@lasued.edu.ng

08036627633

¹Natural Science Education Department, College of Science Education, Lagos State University of Education, Oto/Ijanikin, Lagos, Nigeria

Abstract

The study investigated the role of equitable and quality basic science education at junior secondary school level in promoting integrated science education in tertiary institutions. In order to accomplish this purpose, a descriptive survey research design with a sample of 25 basic science teachers and 345 junior secondary school three basic science students drawn from public and private secondary schools in Lagos State Education District V through simple random sampling technique was used. A 20-items self-constructed questionnaire, validated by experts in science education and with a reliability coefficient of 0.87 was adopted to generate data. The data collected were analysed using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and t-test at 0.05 level of significant using SPSS 23 package. The study revealed that inequitable access, dearth of resources and class size were found to have a notable impact on equitable and quality basic science education. More so, female students usually do not develop interest and motivation to study integrated science as a discipline at tertiary institutions. It was concluded that there is a lack of equitable access to basic science education across different groups, which in turn affected the study of integrated science education in tertiary institutions. The study proposed that increased resources be allocated to basic science education at the junior secondary schools, and a framework for implementing equitable access and quality basic science education should be established in order to ensure that all students have access to adequate resources and learning.

Keywords: Basic Science Education, Equitable, Quality, Integrated Science Education, Parity

Introduction

In the 21st century, science education has long been recognized as the driving force for economic development and improving the well-being of individuals, their communities and nation. Science can be regarded as the linchpin of industrial development and the link between technology and socioeconomic development (Oginni et al., 2023; Danjuma & Adakole 2019). A country's ability to secure good health, fight diseases, protect the environment, produce food for its people and develop new industries and technologies is dependent on the scientific knowledge and skills of its people (Olakanpo, 2015). However, the foundation for advanced scientific knowledge and skills is laid at basic science education levels, which encompassed primary and secondary levels. This subject equips students with foundational knowledge in key disciplines such as biology, chemistry, and physics, laying the groundwork for interdisciplinary learning (Oginni & Saibu, 2019).

Basic science as a subject is taught at basic school level of education (basic 1-9 equivalent to primary 1 - 6 and junior secondary school 1 - 3) as entrenched in the Nigeria 6-3-3-4 system of education, where in, students will have 6 years in primary school, three-year junior secondary school education, three-year senior secondary school, and four years in tertiary institutions.

Integrated science education at tertiary institutions builds upon this foundation by encouraging a multidisciplinary approach to complex issues like climate change, energy sustainability, and public health (Oginni et al., 2024). Recognising the vital role of science education to national development, the Federal Government of Nigeria in the National Policy on Education emphasised that basic science should be taught in such a way to equip students with knowledge and skills to live effectively in the modern age of science and technology (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2014). Saibu et al. (2024) stressed that proper teaching and handling of science subjects especially basic science in schools will result in the training of the minds of students in understanding the world around them, acquisition of appropriate skills capabilities, and with competencies necessary for them to live and contribute to the development of their society.

Despite the importance of basic science in schools, many countries like Nigeria face significant challenges in providing equitable and quality basic science education. In low-income regions, schools often lack basic laboratory equipment, qualified science teachers, and updated curricula (World Bank, 2020). In Nigeria, study has reported that disparities in access to equitable and quality basic science education create significant barriers for many students, particularly those from marginalized communities (Oginni & Saibu, 2019). According to Adesoji and Oginni (2012), these disparities often stem from unequal access to resources, unqualified teachers, and poorly designed curricula that failed to engage learners effectively.

A study by Ayodeji (2018) on the relevance of basic science education in south-west Nigeria found that many factors such as inadequately equipped laboratories, inadequate access to ICT by the in-school youth, low ratio of teacher to students were challenges in majority of the schools. Others factors include lack of textbooks, science equipment and facilities and poorly equipped laboratory rooms (Batomalague, 2015). Large class sizes, inadequate funding, gender disparity, insufficient curriculum resources, poor teaching skills and lack of supports for teachers among other factors further limit the quality of science teaching and learning in Nigerian schools (Okebukola, 1997). Owodunni (2018) conducted a research study on appraisal of the provision of quality basic education in primary schools in Kwali Area Council of Federal Capital Territory, Abuja and reported that it was poor as a result of inadequate human and material resources for the implementation of the curricula. Thus, without access to quality science education, students were deprived of the opportunity to develop the fundamental competencies required for advanced learning, particularly in integrated science programs at tertiary institutions. This gap not only limits individual potential but also undermined societal progress. Equitable and quality basic science education forms the backbone of any nation's scientific and technological advancement. It serves as a critical foundation for fostering scientific literacy, problem-solving skills, and innovation, all of which are essential for addressing global challenges (Oginni & Saibu, 2019). The term equity refers to the principle of fairness and it encompasses a wide variety of educational models, programmes, and strategies that may be considered fair, but not necessarily equal (Uzoka & Igwe, 2015). Equitable and quality science education is effective science teaching which occurs when students learn and achieve many scientific goals and not just being able to repeat scientific knowledge (Omoifo, 2012).

According to UNESCO (2017), equitable education ensures that all students, including those from marginalized communities, have access to quality learning experiences. Quality basic science education involves well-trained teachers, adequate infrastructure, and a curriculum that promotes inquiry-based learning and critical thinking and when these elements are in place, students are better prepared to transition to tertiary education, where integrated science education becomes essential. Additionally, the importance of equitable science education is widely recognized in global frameworks. For instance, the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 4 advocates for inclusive and equitable quality education to ensure lifelong learning opportunities for all (United Nations, 2023). Research has shown that students who receive quality basic science education are better equipped to succeed in higher education, particularly in science-related fields, where critical thinking and problem-solving skills are paramount (Oginni & Saibu, 2019; National Research Council, 2012).

Gender disparities with girls often having limited access to science education due to cultural, economic, and social barriers have been a major discourse among science educators (Oginni et al., 2023). In Nigeria, it is worthy of note is that there is a section of the citizenry that has not taken advantage of the science education that schools have provided. These are girls and women. This has affected the type of education girls and women receive even up to the tertiary institutions. The concern has focused progressively on the consequences of this gender gap for universal scientific literacy and for gender equity in the pursuit of science and technology careers. Fundamentally, interest and desire would have been there at the foundational stage and that is what the female student lack even at the primary and junior secondary school level.

According to Roseline and Azuka (2016), few of the lucky female students who enrolled at the tertiary education level unlike their male counterparts tend to express lack of interest in science related disciplines. This attitude could be associated to the fact that the predominant pattern of teacher interaction with female students to be low as girls received less of their teachers' attention in class. More so, most female students are again confronted with under-involvement in science lessons, variation in the socio-cultural expectations from female to male students, lack of female science teachers as role models among others could

likely be a possible factor that inhibits female choice of career and involvement in science related subjects. Although, there exists a sharp contrast as previous studies by Entwisle and Duckworth (1997) revealed that boys are more oriented towards the hard sciences (physics, math, chemistry, engineering and others) while girls prefer the soft subjects such as human physiology, plant life, zoology among others. Thus, the quest to improve the teaching of basic scientific education has become a paramount factor to determine a country's socio-economic development of the country. Nevertheless, this may be difficult to achieve without the adequate understanding of the current status of science education and the means to improve it. In comparison it can be stated in specifics that students' performance in standardized examination shows the quality of response learners have towards such items. Performance of students in private schools often shows that they perform better than those in public schools, reasons been that the former are often provided with needed facilities to enhance better outcome unlike the latter. However below is the performance of students in Basic Science Education in the past three years in Lagos State.

Table 1: Summary of students' performance in BECE for three years in Lagos State

Year	Private schools		Public schools	
	Merit	Credit	Merit	Credit
2019	66.7%	33.3%	31.7%	68.3%
2020	50.3%	49.7%	44.3%	55.7%
2021	59.1%	40.9%	32.1%	68.9%

BECE Examiner's Report, 2022

Secondary school is the foundation for the development of career choice for students and at the tertiary level they either excel in it or drop out. No wonder stakeholders in the educational sector have advocated for the internalization of basic science education at the primary level so that learners become acclimatized with the futuristic tasks that awaits them in the course of development (Roseline & Azuka 2016). There is no doubt that when students are well abreast with the dynamics that surrounds basic science apparently, the internalization of integrated science education will not be an issue at the tertiary level. Of a truth, the philosophy surrounding the teaching and learning of integrated science cannot be underestimated as it flows through basic science. Effective teaching and learning of basic science will allow for a smooth transmutation to integrated science education a course where specialty will be afforded at the tertiary level.

In Nigeria, despite the laudable goals of basic science as a catalyst to the study of integrated science education at the tertiary level, students and Nigerians are yet to harness the benefits of science in our respective schools since it has failed to produce skilled human resources, low population by prospective applicants to study integrated science, inability to create inventions among others which are needed for sustainable development as a result one is forced to probe the equitable access to quality basic science education. Integrated science education in tertiary institutions emphasizes the interconnectedness of scientific disciplines, enabling students to approach complex problems holistically. This approach aligns with the demands of the 21st century, where interdisciplinary collaboration is essential for innovation and problem-solving.

Tertiary institutions that adopt integrated science education models are better positioned to produce graduates who can tackle such multifaceted challenges of the society. The transition from basic to tertiary science education is seamless when students have a strong foundation in basic science. Equitable and quality basic science education ensures that students acquire the necessary knowledge, skills, and attitudes to excel in integrated science programs at the tertiary level. In view of this, the study was designed to investigate equitable and quality basic science education as a catalyst for integrated science education in tertiary institutions.

Objectives of the study are to:

1. Identify possible factors that impede equitable and quality basic science education in Nigeria private and public schools.
2. Find out if equitable and quality basic science education promotes the study of integrated science education in tertiary institutions.

Null Hypotheses

Two hypotheses were designed to guide the thought of this study.

- Ho₁: Prevalent possible factors affecting equitable and quality basic science education do not significantly affect study of integrated science education at the tertiary institutions.
- Ho₂: Equitable and Quality basic science education does not significantly promote integrated science education in Nigeria tertiary institutions by gender.

Methodology

The descriptive survey methodology was used for analysis of data in this study. This design gave opportunity to study small and large population (universe) by selecting and studying samples chosen from the population in order to discover the relative incidence, distribution and interrelations of sociological and psychological variables. The researchers identified the composition of secondary school students as its population, while the target population comprised of basic science teachers and JSS 3 students (prospective JSSCE candidates) in Lagos State. A sample of 25 basic science teachers and 345 junior secondary school three students drawn from public and private schools in Lagos State Education District V through simple random sampling technique was used.

A self-designed questionnaire titled “Questionnaire on Equitable and Quality Primary and Secondary Basic Science Education” was used to collect data for the study. The questionnaire was divided into two sections A and B. Section A generated items on students’ bio-data while Section B generated 20 closed ended items statements. The instrument was designed on 4-Likert scale type of strongly agreed (SA) - 4, agreed (A) - 3, disagreed (D) - 2 and strongly disagreed (SD) - 1 respectively. The validity of the instrument was determined as copies of these instruments were sent to three science education experts in University of Ibadan, Ibadan. After modification, removal and addition of certain items, the final copy of the instrument was acclaimed to meet construct validity. However, the reliability of was determined on 15 students not participating in this work through the use of split-half reliability method. An index value of 0.89 was derived, showing positively high correlation meaning that the instrument is very reliable and suitable for this work. With the aid of SPSS Version 23, the researchers analysed the data generated using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and t-test analysis was done at 0.05 significant level.

Results

H₀₁: Prevalent possible factors affecting equitable and quality basic science education do not significantly affect study of integrated science education at the tertiary institutions.

Table 2: ANOVA showing possible factors affecting equitable and quality basic science education

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	8.62 ^a	5	1.73	2.85	.02
Intercept	33.39	1	33.39	55.20	.00
Finance constraints	3.12	1	3.12	5.16	.02
Inequitable access	4.86	1	4.86	8.05	.01
Dearth of resources	.43	1	.43	.72	.04
Class size	.27	1	.28	.46	.04
Students’ age	.01	1	.01	.01	.01
Error	117.38	264	.61		
Total	1808.00	370			
Corrected Total	126.00	369			

a. R Squared = .0878 (Adjusted R Squared = .0794)

Table 2 revealed that variables affecting equitable and quality basic science education do significantly promote study of integrated science at the tertiary institutions. Financial constraints: $F(1, 264)=5.16$; $p=0.02$; inequitable access $F(1,264)=8.05$; $p=0.01$; dearth of resources $F(1,264)=0.72$; $p=0.04$; class size $F(1,264)=0.46$; $p=0.04$; students’ age $F(1,264)=0.01$; $p=0.01$. This implies that financial constraints, inequitable access, dearth of resources, class size and students’ age accounted for 9.0%, 12.2%, 15%, 20.4% and 25% respectively for the variance. Therefore, the null hypothesis which state that prevalent possible factors affecting equitable and quality basic science education do not significantly affect study of integrated science education at the tertiary institutions is rejected.

H₀₂: Equitable and Quality basic science education does not significantly promote integrated science education in Nigeria tertiary institutions by gender.

Table 3: t-test analysis showing equitable and quality basic science education promote integrated science education in Nigeria tertiary institutions by gender

Gender	N	X	SD	Df	P	t-cal.	t-tab.
Female	187	1.95	0.45	198	0.02	3.34	1.96
Male	158	2.45	0.74				

The analysis on Table 3 showed that more female students were captured than their male counterparts. The female students had a mean and standard deviation values respectively as 1.95 and 0.45 as against their male counterparts that had 2.45 and 0.74 as respective mean and standard deviation. The t-test value of 3.34 was obtained and at degree of freedom 198, the t-ratio value of 1.96 was derived. Since the t-cal was greater than the t-tab, the null hypothesis which stated that equitable and quality basic science education does not significantly promote integrated science education in Nigeria tertiary institutions by gender is rejected.

Discussion of Findings

From hypothesis one, it was revealed that variables (financial constraints, inequitable access, dearth of ICT, class size and students' age) that affect equitable and quality basic science education do significantly promote integrated science in Nigeria tertiary institutions. No doubt exposure and quality education both at the primary and secondary levels of education definitely goes a long way to drive the productive integrated science education even till the tertiary institutions. This finding tallies with the results by Otemuyiwa and Odiagbe (2021), and Owodunni (2018) that the quality of the provision of basic schools was poor, resulting from the non-adequacy of some human and material resources for the implementation of the curricula. Also, the finding of Otemuyiwa (2017) affirmed that non-functional basic science equipment and laboratory, basic technology and non-functional laboratory, lack of instructional facilities and materials such as curricular and accompanying teachers' guide, lack of computers and accessories among others.

This study outcome is in consonance with earlier studies carried out by Oginni and Saibu (2019) and Schiebinger (2010), which alluded that financial constraints, inequitable access to quality education, dearth of ICT facilities, large class size and students age goes a long way to promote the study of integrated science education at the tertiary institution level. They were of the opinion that integrated science education remains one subject that touches on the developmental phase of humans, designed to develop skills and abilities of individuals with respect to STEM, drive positive thinking and exposure to group dynamics, improvement in latent abilities and guides quality decision making process. However, the finding from this study did not conform with the one reported by Ekwukoma et al. (2016) that qualified and adequate teachers were available for the implementation of the 9-Year Basic Education Curriculum.

The second hypothesis revealed that equitable and quality basic science education significantly promote integrated science education at the tertiary level by gender as male students tended to gravitate to study integrated science education in Nigeria tertiary institutions than their female counterparts. The finding was in line with Oginni et al. (2023), Oginni and Saibu (2019), and Roseline and Azuka (2016), which informed that few of the lucky female students who enroll at the tertiary education level unlike their male counterparts attributed their decline in involvement to lack of interest, desire and motivation to study science related disciplines. This attitude could be associated to the fact that the predominant pattern of teacher interaction with female students is very infinitesimal as girls received less of their teachers' attention in class.

More so, most female students were confronted with under-involvement in science lessons, variation in the socio-cultural expectations from female to male students among others could likely be possible factors that inhibit female choice of career and involvement in science related subjects. Although there exists a sharp contrast as previous studies by Entwisle and Duckworth (1997) revealed that boys are more oriented towards the perceived difficult sciences (physics, math, chemistry, engineering and others) while girls prefer the simple science subjects such as human physiology, plant life, zoology among others.

Conclusion

The findings of this study revealed that various factors significantly influence the promotion of integrated science education at the tertiary level. Financial constraints, inequitable access, dearth of resources, class size, and students' age were found to have a notable impact on equitable and quality basic science education, which in turn affected the study of integrated science education in Nigeria tertiary institutions. The results further showed that gender played a significant role, with

participation of female students in the study of science related subjects very low and discouraging due to lack of interest and motivation than their male counterparts. These findings emphasized the necessity of addressing these disparities to ensure a more inclusive and effective integrated science education at the tertiary institutions. The study further concluded that equitable and quality primary and junior secondary basic science education is a fundamental prerequisite to achieving integrated science education at the tertiary institutions.

Recommendations

From the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Governments and educational institutions should allocate more financial resources to improve facilities, provide adequate teaching materials, and offer financial assistance to students facing economic hardships.
2. Policies should be implemented to ensure that students from underprivileged backgrounds have equal access to quality science education, including scholarship programs and infrastructural development in rural areas.
3. Schools should adopt policies that limit class sizes to manageable levels to promote better student-teacher interactions, ensuring a more effective teaching and learning process.
4. Special initiatives and awareness programs should be developed to encourage female students to engage more in integrated science education while sustaining the achievements of male students.
5. Curriculum designers should consider students' age variations when structuring science programs, incorporating age-appropriate learning techniques to maximize comprehension and retention.

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